

Elliptical Limit-Cycle Oscillations of the Mosquito Flagellum

Justin Faber^{1, a)} and Dolores Bozovic^{1, 2, b)}

¹⁾*Department of Physics & Astronomy, University of California, Los Angeles, California 90095, USA.*

²⁾*California NanoSystems Institute, University of California, Los Angeles, California 90095, USA.*

^{a)}*Electronic mail: faber@physics.ucla.edu*

^{b)}*Electronic mail: bozovic@physics.ucla.edu.*

Abstract. Male mosquitoes exhibit active, spontaneous motion of their flagella, a mechanism believed to aid in the detection of faint sounds produced by flying female mosquitoes. These self-sustained oscillations have been observed in several species of mosquito, with recent studies focusing on the species known to transmit infectious diseases. While the flagellum has two spatial degrees of freedom, measurements performed thus far have used laser interferometry to record the motion along one direction only. The shape of the flagellar motion in the 2-dimensional plane therefore remains unknown. We present a simple numerical model of this system, consisting of a passive harmonic oscillator driven by active Hopf oscillators configured in a circular arrangement. Our numerical simulations indicate that planar motion is unstable for such a system and the flagellum instead moves along elliptical trajectories. Lastly, we discuss the potential advantages that this elliptical motion may have on signal detection and localization.

INTRODUCTION

The auditory system of mosquitoes exhibits several parallels to those of vertebrates, including sensitivity to weak signals [1], nonlinear attenuation of strong signals [2], and active, autonomous oscillations of their sensors [3, 4]. The mosquito flagellum acts as a directionally sensitive receiver, responding to acoustic velocity fields, and aligning its oscillations along the direction of the incoming sound. The rod-like flagellum moves like an inverted pendulum, with two spacial degrees of freedom. The base of the flagellum is attached to the Johnson's organ, a bowl-like structure that houses thousands of scolopidia. These scolopidia act as the stretch receptors in the joints of insects, converting mechanical displacements into neurological signals. The scolopidia are also believed to act as active motors, giving rise to self-sustained flagellar oscillations [5]. This autonomous motion exhibits many parallels to the spontaneous oscillations measured in vertebrates and has been shown to amplify weak signals, thereby aiding auditory detection [6].

A previous numerical model of the mosquito auditory system included microscopic details of the active motors and demonstrated that self-sustained oscillations of the passive flagellum can arise from the impulsive forces generated by the active motors, provided that the motors are able to operate in synchrony [7]. Other numerical studies have shown that the main macroscopic features of this sensory system are captured when the motors are represented by generic Hopf oscillators [8, 9]. While these numerical models explained a number of experimentally measured phenomena of the system, they considered the flagellar motion to occur along one spacial dimension only.

In the present study, we consider both spacial degrees of the flagellum and propose that motion may arise in which the flagellum traces out the surface of a cone. We refer to this motion as “elliptical” or “circular”, based on the shape traced out by the flagellar tip. We present a numerical model of this complex system based on the circular arrangement of active scolopidia. We represent these active motors as generic Hopf oscillators, while representing the flagellum as a passive, 2-dimensional harmonic oscillator, through which the active motors are mechanically coupled. We constrain the parameter space of this high-dimensional system using experimental measurements, leaving just two free parameters. We then explore the dynamics of this system throughout the parameter space, finding stable fixed points and stable limit cycles. Finally, we show that planar motion of the flagellum is unstable, and that the stable limit-cycle state instead produces elliptical oscillations of the flagellum. We propose that the physical system utilizes these elliptical trajectories for sensitive detection and accurate localization of sound.

NUMERICAL MODEL

We use a dimensionless model of the form,

$$\frac{d^2Z}{dt^2} + 2\zeta \frac{dZ}{dt} + Z = \bar{z} \quad (1)$$

FIGURE 1. Illustration of the connection between the j^{th} active element (red) and the passive flagellum (blue). The position of the flagellum with respect to its equilibrium position is described by complex variable, $Z(t)$. The position of the j^{th} active element is described by complex variable, $z_j(t)$. These two components are connected by an elastic element of stiffness, k . We consider only the projection of this coupling force onto the unit vector, $\hat{\psi}_j$.

$$\frac{dz_j}{dt} = (\mu_j + i\omega_j)z_j - |z_j|^2 z_j + k[(\gamma Z - z_j) \cdot \hat{\psi}_j] \hat{\psi}_j, \quad (2)$$

where $Z(t)$ represents the position of the flagellum as viewed from above ($Z(t) = X(t) + iY(t)$). $z_j(t)$ represents the dynamic state of the j^{th} active element ($z_j(t) = x_j(t) + iy_j(t)$). The mean field of the active elements is given by $\bar{z}(t) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N z_j(t)$. ζ represents the damping ratio of the passive components, μ_j and ω_j denote the control parameter and characteristic frequency of the j^{th} active element, and k represents the coupling strength between the active elements and the passive flagellum. γ denotes the ratio of the combined stiffness of the connecting elements to the total stiffness of the system (flagellar pivot stiffness and connection stiffness together). For our choice of numerical values, we consider prior measurements of the flagellar stiffness of several mosquito species [6]. Based on the measured changes of these values induced by introducing channel blockers, we estimate the stiffness ratio to be within the range of 0.25 to 0.75. We will use $\gamma = 0.5$, unless stated otherwise.

We approximate the force between active and passive elements to be proportional to the projection of the difference vector, $\gamma Z - z_j$, onto the line that connects their origins (Fig. 1). This approximation holds for displacements that are small with respect to the distance between the attachment points of the scolopidia. Considering that the flagellum pivots only a fraction of a degree during signal detection, this should constitute a reasonable approximation [1]. One of the advantages of introducing this approximation is that the length scale of the Johnston's organ drops out of the model. Further, this approximation removes the assumption that the active motors move in two spacial dimensions. While we describe the dynamics of the active elements by 2-dimensional limit cycles, the forces they impose on the flagellum are individually 1-dimensional. This means that 2-dimensional motion of the flagellum is a collective phenomenon, arising from the configuration and connection of the elements, rather than the circular dynamics of the individual components.

We assume a random, Gaussian distribution of characteristic frequencies centered at the characteristic frequency of the passive components, $\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \omega_j = 1$. Further, we set the standard deviation of this distribution to be $\sigma_\omega = 0.2$, approximating the neuronal tuning observed experimentally [10]. Measurements of the male flagellum exhibit underdamped behavior, even when in the passive state [6]. We therefore expect the damping ratio to be confined to $0.1 < \zeta < 1$, consistent with a numerical model of the elephant mosquito, *Toxorhynchites* [7]. For the current study, we fix the damping ratio to be $\zeta = 0.3$. We use $N = 1000$, approximating the number of active elements in the male mosquito. Lastly, we assume identical control parameters for the active elements ($\mu_j = \mu$). These simplifications leave only two arbitrary free parameters (μ and k) in the model.

FIGURE 2. (A) Flagellar dynamics with the trajectory beginning along the red arrow ($\mu = k = 1$). The initial conditions were chosen as an attempt to produce planar motion. (B) Flagellar dynamics in the $X - Y$ plane for a grid of μ and k values. Transients were removed to show the dynamic state of the system (fixed point or limit cycle).

RESULTS

Numerical simulations of this dynamical system indicate that, for a wide range of parameters, the flagellum exhibits autonomous, circular motion in the $X - Y$ plane. These limit cycles are stable to perturbations and variations of the initial conditions. Stable planar motion of the flagellum was not observed for any parameter combination. We attempted to produce planar motion by choosing the initial position and velocity of the flagellum to be anti-parallel (Fig. 2A). For all attempts, the flagellum quickly settled onto its stable circular limit cycle, suggesting that planar motion of the flagellum is unstable. This simple model considers the drag of the flagellum to be symmetric in all directions, and therefore produces circular limit cycles. However, the physical system consists of a feather-like structure, likely having different drag coefficients in the two degrees of freedom. We therefore anticipate that its oscillations will be attenuated along the axis of maximal drag, resulting in elliptical limit cycles.

The amplitude of the flagellar limit cycle increases with increasing μ , in a manner similar to the amplitude of a single Hopf oscillator (Fig. 2B). For weak coupling strength (k), the motion of the Hopf oscillators is weakly correlated, resulting in substantial averaging out of the active forces, thus rendering the flagellum quiescent. For larger values of the coupling strength, the motion of the Hopf oscillators synchronizes, producing circular flagellar motion. For excessively high values of the coupling strength, the frequency dispersion of the Hopf oscillators causes quenching of the autonomous motion, yielding a quiescent flagellum. In dynamical systems theory, this phenomenon is known as *Oscillation Death* [11].

DISCUSSION

We have developed a numerical model of the auditory system of the male mosquito, treating the flagellum as a passive harmonic oscillator, and the active elements of the Johnston's organ as Hopf oscillators. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first numerical model of this system that accounts for the circular configuration of the active elements. Our numerical simulations indicate that the autonomous motion of the flagellum is elliptical, rather than planar. We note that, although the active motors in this model contain two degrees of freedom, we have considered only the dominant direction of the forces each motor exerts on the flagellum. The individual forces from the active motors are therefore 1-dimensional, suggesting that the 2-dimensional motion of the flagellum is a collective phenomenon, rather than one

that depends on the microscopic details of the motors.

Male mosquitoes are believed to utilize their self-sustained oscillations to aid in the detection of potential mates [6]. The transition between quiescent and oscillatory behavior can arise in several ways according to our numerical model. Adjusting the control parameter can move the system between these two types of behavior. Alternatively, adjusting the damping ratio of the system can cause a transition between the two states. Mosquitoes have been shown to adjust the tension in the bristle-like fibrillae on their flagellum during mating times [12, 13]. We therefore speculate that modulation of the damping ratio of the flagellum provides the insect with a way to adjust the dynamical state of its auditory system.

Future work entails obtaining experimental measurements of self-sustained flagellar oscillations in 2 dimensions. Our numerical model predicts that planar flagellar motion is unstable. Instead, we propose that the flagellum oscillates in elliptical motion and that, in the presence of sufficiently strong stimulus, the major axis of the ellipse should align with the direction of the sound source. Further, we speculate that the information of the sound intensity is encoded in the eccentricity of this elliptical orbit.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of the International Human Frontier Science Program (IHFSP).

REFERENCES

1. M. C. Göpfert and D. Robert, “Nanometre-range acoustic sensitivity in male and female mosquitoes,” *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. B* **267**, 453 (2000), <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2000.1021>.
2. B. Nadrowski, T. Effertz, P. R. Senthilan, and M. C. Göpfert, “Antennal hearing in insects – new findings, new questions,” *Hear. Res.* **273**, 7 (2011), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heares.2010.03.092>.
3. M. C. Göpfert and R. M. Hennig, “Hearing in insects,” *Annu. Rev. Entomol.* **61**, 257 (2016), <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ento-010715-023631>.
4. B. Warren and M. Nowotny, “Bridging the gap between mammal and insect ears – a comparative and evolutionary view of sound-reception,” *Front. Ecol. Evol.* **9**, 1 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2021.667218>.
5. M. C. Göpfert and D. Robert, “Active auditory mechanics in mosquitoes,” *Proc. R. Soc. Lond. B* **268**, 333 (2001), <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2000.1376>.
6. M. P. Su, M. Andrés, N. Boyd-Gibbins, J. Somers, and J. T. Albert, “Sex and species specific hearing mechanisms in mosquito flagellar ears,” *Nat. Comm.* **9**, 3911 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-06388-7>.
7. D. Avitabile, M. Homer, A. R. Champneys, J. C. Jackson, and D. Robert, “Mathematical modelling of the active hearing process in mosquitoes,” *J. R. Soc. Interface* **7**, 105 (2009), <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsif.2009.0091>.
8. J. C. Jackson, J. F. C. Windmill, V. G. Pook, and D. Robert, “Synchrony through twice-frequency forcing for sensitive and selective auditory processing,” *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **106**, 10177 (2009), <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0901727106>.
9. J. F. C. Windmill, J. C. Jackson, V. G. Pook, and D. Robert, “Frequency doubling by active in vivo motility of mechanosensory neurons in the mosquito ear,” *R. Soc. Open Sci.* **5**, 171082 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.171082>.
10. D. N. Lapshin and D. D. Vorontsov, “Frequency organization of the johnston’s organ in male mosquitoes (diptera, culicidae),” *J. Exp. Biol.* **220**, 3927 (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1242/jeb.152017>.
11. A. Koseska, E. Volkov, and J. Kurths, “Oscillation quenching mechanisms: Amplitude vs. oscillation death,” *Phys. Rep.* **531**, 173 (2013), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physrep.2013.06.001>.
12. H. F. Nijhout, “Control of antennal hair erection in male mosquitoes,” *Biol. Bull.* **153**, 591 (1977), <https://doi.org/10.2307/1540608>.
13. J. D. Charlwood and M. D. R. Jones, “Mating in the mosquito, *Anopheles gambiae* s.l.” *Physiol. Entomol.* **5**, 315 (1980), <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3032.1980.tb00241.x>.
14. K. S. Boo and A. G. Richards, “Fine structure of the scolopidia in the johnston’s organ of male *Aedes aegypti* (L.) (diptera: Culicidae),” *Int. J. Insect Morphol. Embryol.* **4**, 549–566 (1975), [https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7322\(75\)90031-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0020-7322(75)90031-8).

COMMENTS AND QUESTIONS

[Morgan Thienpont]: Interesting paper and remarkable subject. I am a bit confused here, does “planar motion” not just mean 2d motion? Then how can it be “elliptical instead” of planar? Or do you actually mean elliptical instead of circular? Maybe for Figure 1 it would be interesting to indicate what the active and passive elements are and also the flagellum itself. It took me quite some time going back and forth.

[Justin Faber (author)]: Thank you for the helpful comments. I see how that is confusing. By “circular/elliptical motion”, we mean that the whole rod-like flagellum is moving in three dimensions, fixed at the base, and tracing out a cone-like surface. When viewed from above (along the axis of the flagellum’s resting position), the motion of the tip will be moving in a circle/ellipse. However, by “planar motion”, we are referring to motion where the full structure of the flagellum remains in a plane. In this case, when viewed from above, the tip of the flagellum will be moving back and forth along a straight line. We will be sure to clarify this in the text. We will also add a clearer description of Figure 1, being sure to identify the passive and active elements.

[Thomas Effertz]: Thank you for your interesting point of view on the topic. Coming from the *Drosophila* field myself, I am not 100% familiar with the anatomy of Johnston’s organ in mosquitoes and might be a bit rusty. That said, is there an anatomical correlation between your simulation and what you see in the organ? As you mentioned, the flagellum is more reminiscent of a feather, which would suggest one direction of highest sensitivity, is this maybe mirrored in a different distribution of JO neurons? Speaking of anatomy, is it possible to include the different directional drags of the flagellum in female vs. male mosquito antennae into your model? If I am not mistaken, there should also be a finite-element model of mosquito flagella out there.

Also, while you assumed 1,000 active elements in your model, the mosquito Johnston’s organ comprises ca 16,000 scolopidia, I think. Was there a specific reason for choosing a lower number of active elements or would you even expect a different outcome when modeling with a higher number of active elements? Having measured motion of mosquito antennae myself with a single point LDV (granted, long time ago), I do not recall observing a loss of signal that could be due to perpendicular motion of the flagellum relative to the sound source/wide plane of the “feather” flagellum. The motion might not have been sufficiently large that the laser beam would lose a reflection point. To this point, it would be beneficial, if you could add a displacement range for your proposed circular motion at or near the tip of the flagellum. That could inform *in vivo* experiments and would be a good comparison point between your model and the real organ.

One last little thing. Up until the results section, you are talking about elliptical motion, elliptical trajectory etc. but in the results section you start with “circular motion in the X-Y plane”, this through me for a second. Before that, you only used “circular” to describe the anatomy of the organ, not the motion you are seeing. The same thing happened when looking at Figure 2 for the first time. It is a bit confusing for the reader when you speak of elliptical motion but what one sees is circular. Here I would suggest incorporating earlier in the text that due to the feather like structure, although your model predicts circular motion, the motion will likely be elliptical with the sides parallel to the “feather” being squished together. You do that later in the discussion but when first reading the results or seeing Figure 2 it is confusing. Overall, I quite like the approach and am looking forward to your *in vivo* measurements.

[Justin Faber (author)]: Our model is based on a simplified version of the geometry of the Johnston’s organ. If we assume the displacements of the flagellum are small in comparison to its length, then we can map the 3-dimensional dynamics onto our 2-dimensional model, which consists of a circular configuration of active elements. We assumed a uniform distribution of the active elements around this circle. We based this off of images in the literature. We have not found any evidence for a nonuniform distribution. Also, you bring up a good point about the asymmetry in the drag of the flagellum. We have accounted for this in the model and will include this in a future publication. You are correct that the additional drag in one direction attenuates the motion along that axis, producing elliptical trajectories. If we get estimates of this drag ratio, we can then predict what level of eccentricity of the ellipse we would expect to find in experimental measurements.

Based on the results of [14], we should expect about 7000-7500 scolopidia per pedicel/ear, and about twice as many neurons. Each active element in our model represents a scolopidium. We used 1000 active elements as a conservative estimate of this number, since we cannot be sure that all elements are contributing energy at the same time. Or, perhaps there is a division of labor where some act as sensors while others act as amplifiers. We did try varying this number in the numerical model and found that beyond 100 active elements, there is not a noticeable change in the dynamics.

We will be sure to make the other changes you suggested pertaining to circular vs. elliptical motion. Thanks again for your helpful comments.